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Review Article

**PIOGLITAZONE USE AND BLADDER CANCER –
A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW**Hyder Osman Mirghani¹, MD, Ibrahim Altedlawi Albalawi², MD¹Faculty of Medicine, University of Tabuk, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia,²Faculty of Medicine, University of Tabuk, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia**Abstract:**

Introduction: Pioglitazone is a second line treatment of diabetes mellitus with insulin-sensitizing properties. The association of pioglitazone with bladder cancer is controversial. We aimed to summarize the results regarding pioglitazone use and bladder cancer risk

Material and Methods: A systematic literature search on the relevant literature on pioglitazone and bladder cancer during the period from January 2008 to December 2018 was carried out, studies on animals and human studies in the MEDLINE web of Science, and Pubmed were included using the keywords pioglitazone, thiazolidinedione, and bladder cancer.

Results: Out of 156 articles, 40 manuscripts stands after duplication removal and applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria (three experimental studies, thirteen reviews, and twenty-four cohorts). The results were contradicting across all studies, with some showed the association of pioglitazone with bladder cancer with a cumulative dose of 28gm and two years duration, while others reported no association.

Conclusion: The evidence regarding the association between pioglitazone and bladder cancer were mixed and some authors suggested conflicts of interests. Pioglitazone has protective cardiovascular effects especially among patients with stroke, it's used in a small dose in short duration may outweigh the inconclusive association with bladder cancer.

Keywords: Pioglitazone, Dose, and duration, Bladder cancer.

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INTRODUCTION:

People with type 2 diabetes are at an increased risk of bladder cancer; it is said that pioglitazone further increases the risk in spite of the fact that the published evidence is mixed [1].

Pioglitazone activates peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors (PPARs) increasing insulin sensitivity in adipose, muscle, and liver to improve glucose utilization and decrease glucose production. These drugs increase HDL, lower TG and blood pressure, and reduce visceral fat. It also, decrease microalbuminuria, increase lipoprotein, LDL, and weight so contraindicated in 3&4 heart failure. It had been linked to some malignancies in animal studies like urinary bladder and colon so not prescribed in patients with family history adenomatous polyposis coli. Osteoporosis and macular edema risks. The statement is to be skeptical and prudent in their use awaiting further studies [2,3].

There is a growing safety concern regarding the potential effects of pioglitazone in increasing bladder cancer, although large clinical studies [4, 5] showed discordant results which led to more debate, however, the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) [6] warned about this risk and recommended the treating doctors to weigh the benefit and risk before prescribing the drug and that the patient to contact their doctor in case of hesitancy, burning micturition, or haematuria. A detection, confounding, or section bias cannot be excluded in the studies that showed a relationship of pioglitazone and bladder cancer. Furthermore, pioglitazone is mainly used as a second or third line treatment in patients not controlled with metformin or sulphonylureas, so patients initiating pioglitazone usually have inadequate glycemic control and a long duration of diabetes mellitus [5].

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES:

We conducted this review to assess up to date evidence regarding the relationship of pioglitazone and bladder cancer.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

An electronic search was done for relevant literature published during the period from January 2008 to December 2018 in the Medline and PubMed database, the keywords pioglitazone, thiazolidinediones, and bladder cancer were used along with the Boolean operators AND or OR. Articles in English on animals and human and reviews were included, forward and backward charring for articles cited in retrieved publication was applied to get relevant results. The two authors searched and recovered the manuscripts

independently for the second stage selection process to avoid duplication of the titles and abstracts, analysis of the relevant data was done by the first author. Figure 1. Showed the results of the literature search

Inclusion criteria:

Previous reviews and experimental studies on animals and cancer cell lines and studies on humans including case-reports and cohorts.

Exclusion criteria: Articles not stating the number of the study sample

Statistical analysis:

The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS, version 20, New York) was used for the data analysis including the article type number of participants, the duration of follow-up, and the cumulative dose.

RESULTS:

The initial number of manuscripts was 156, the number reduced to 46 after removing duplication and stands at 40 after applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria of which three were experimental study, thirteen review articles, and eighteen retrospective studies conducted among humans. Table 1 &2.

Out of 40 articles included: There were three experimental studies and thirty-seven studies on humans (13 reviews including randomized control studies and cohorts, four case-control studies, two longitudinal studies, three population-based studies, and 15 retrospective studies). The current review showed contradicting data. All the reviews except two (one showed no association, and the other showed contradicting results) concluded the association (mild to a moderate association, especially with two years duration and a cumulative dose of 28gms). The contradiction was found in case-control and retrospective studies. All the animal studied showed no association of pioglitazone and bladder cancer, in fact, one study showed a beneficial effect of pioglitazone. However, they suggest a "urolithiasis hypothesis" for the development of bladder cancer.

Figure 1: Flowchart of events in the literature search**Table 01. The relationship of pioglitazone with bladder cancer (animal studies)**

Author	Year	Model	Duration	Results	Comments
Sato et al.	2011	Male Rats	2years	Increased	The increased cancer risk may be due to Microcrystalluria
Tseng et al.	2012	Rats and mice		Increased in male rats but not in mice,	Cannot be generalized to human
Yang et al.	2018	Rats		Beneficial	Suggest that pioglitazone may be beneficial for diabetic patients with bladder cancer through decreased the expression of p53

Table 02.The relationship of pioglitazone with bladder cancer (human studies)

Author	year	Study type	Duration	Patients number	results
Lewis et al.	2011	A longitudinal cohort	193,099 patients		Use for more than 2 years was weakly associated with increased risk
Piccinni et al.	2011	Analysis of FDA adverse events reporting			association between pioglitazone and bladder cancer
Tseng et al.	2012	Review of one trial and observational studies			Contradicting results, some found imbalance between pioglitazone users and placebo, one study showed no relationship between the drug and bladder cancer, the risk may be due to confounders
Tseng et al.	2012	A population-based study	1000000	3years	No significant association
Azoulay et al.	2012	A nested case-control study	115,727	10 years	Association of bladder cancer with a cumulative dose of 28gms and 24 months
Zhu et al.	2012	A meta-analysis of five studies	2,350,908		Association of bladder cancer with a cumulative dose of 28gms and 12-24 months duration, the association was stronger with duration >24 months
Colmers et al.	2012	A meta-analysis of 4 RCTs, 5 cohort studies and 1 case-control study.	2,657,365 patients		The limited evidence supports the association of pioglitazone with bladder cancer
Song et al.	2012	Retrospective case-control study	329 vs. 658 controls		No association
Neuman n et al.	2012	A population-based study	1,491,060	42 months	Pioglitazone was associated with a significant increase in bladder cancer
Mamtani et al.	2012	A retrospective cohort	18 459 pioglitazone and 41 396 sulphonyl ureas		>5 years use may be associated with bladder cancer
Hsiao et al.	2013	A retrospective nested case-control study	3,412 cases vs. 17,060 controls		Association if used \geq 2 years
Vallarino et al.	2013	A retrospective cohort among patients taking pioglitazone or insulin	56,536 patients	1.9-2.2 years	No significant increase in bladder cancer compared to insulin
Wie et al.	2013	A Retrospective Cohort	207714		No significant increase of bladder cancer compared with other antidiabetic medications
Fujimoto et al.	2013	retrospective	663		No significant association
Bazelier et al.	2013	A population-based study	179,056		No increased risk
Kostapa	2013	A review			No evidence of increased cancer

nos et al.					
Bosetti et al.	2013	A meta-analysis of 3 case-control studies and 14 cohort studies			A modest increase risk with prolonged use
Ferwana et al.	2013	A meta-analysis of five studies	215 142 patients	44 months	Slightly increased risk
Kuo et al.	2013	A retrospective nested case-control study	259 cases and 1036 controls		No association with BC
Turner et al.	2014	A review of five randomized trials and 13 observational studies	2.607878		Increased with pioglitazone both at 12-24 months and >24 months and cumulative dose of 28gms, no association was found with rosiglitazone
Lee et al.	2014	A longitudinal cohort	34,970	4 years	No association
Balaji et al.	2014	A retrospective study	5079 cancer patient		No association
Jin et al.	2014	A retrospective cohort	101,953 control patients and 11,240 pioglitazone		Association with bladder cancer even at 15mg and 6 months duration
He et al.	2014	A meta-analysis of 10 studies	2,596,856 diabetic patients		Increase cancer especially in men with cumulative dose and duration
Lewis et al.	2015	Cohort and nested case-control analyses	193,099 for the cohort and 464 vs. 464 controls, and 10 cohorts including 236,507	2.8 years	No increased risk
Levin et al.	2015	a multipopulation pooled, cumulative exposure analysis	1.01 million persons	4-7.4 years	The cumulative use was not associated with BC
Gupta et al.	2015	A retrospective analysis	2222		No association
Tuccori et al.	2016	Population-based	145,806	Taking pioglitazone from 2000-2013, followed for 1 year after	Duration and dose-responsive increase with pioglitazone but not rosiglitazone
Vallabh	2016	Two cohorts	260	5 years	No association

ajosyula et al.			patients		
Han et al	2016	nested case-control study	47,738 patients		No associations
Mackenzie et al.	2016	A retrospective cohort	1,161,443 prevalent and 320,090 incident	38 months	the incidence of bladder cancer increased with duration of pioglitazone use in a prevalent cohort, but not an incident cohort
Korhonen et al.	2016	A retrospective cohort	pioglitazone (n=56 337), drugs other than pioglitazone (n=317 109)	2.9 years	No evidence of association with BC
Li et al.	2017	A review of 14 studies			Increase BC in European male with >12 months duration
Tang et al.	2018	Review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials and observational studies			Pioglitazone may be associated with bladder cancer in a dose and duration dependent manner, screening is advised.
Yan et al.	2018	Review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials and observational studies			Pioglitazone is associated with bladder cancer in high doses, no association in RCTs
Davidson and Pan	2018	A meta-analysis			Weak association
Garry et al.	2018	A comparative study from the beneficiary	N=38 700), DPP-4s N=82 552, and sulfonylureas N = 126 104		Increased risk compared to DPP-4 and sulphonylureas attenuated after drug withdrawal

DISCUSSION:

Animal studies:

A meta-analysis of animal studies [7] found that males and females rats do not develop bladder cancer even when exposed to very high doses. The thiazolidinediones are rarely excreted in the urine, but a receptor-mediated PPAR effect cannot be excluded. Some suggest a "urolithiasis hypothesis" referring to the formation of urinary solids and calculi, which subsequently causes bladder necrosis, regenerative proliferation, hypertrophy, and cancer.

Whether this applies to human is not understood. In contradiction Satos et al. [8] concluded that: Microcrystalluria appears to be involved in the development of the advanced stage proliferative lesions in bladder tumorigenesis induced by pioglitazone in male rats. A recent in vitro study conducted by Yang et al.[9] using urothelial transitional epithelium from rats showed that pioglitazone did not promote malignant alterations. Furthermore, the study stated that pioglitazone might be helpful for diabetic patients with bladder cancer.

Studies on humans:

Lewis et al. [10] reported a weak association of bladder cancer and pioglitazone use after 24 months in Northern California, the follow-up of the same study [11] published in 2015 showed no association of the drug with bladder cancer. The association of pioglitazone and bladder cancer observed by Piccinni et al. [12] in 2011 was based on the FDA registry of adverse drug registry (case and non-case), the observation needs more constant epidemiological studies. Tseng et al. [13] in their review in 2012 showed conflicting results, the only randomized control study included showed an imbalance but after a blind assessment they concluded that the balance might not be due to pioglitazone. The observational studies reviewed showed contradicting results, those from the US and France suggest that the use of pioglitazone > two years might be associated with bladder cancer, while a study conducted in Taiwan showed no association even after three years. Furthermore, the studies are conducted on registries and may be prone to indication bias (pioglitazone is a third line medication and the user may be old, with long duration of diabetes, and poor glycemic control. The results may also be inflated with selection and information bias and confounders. Tseng et al. [14] published a population-based study from a 4-year registry including a million patients (54928 patients with diabetes) and found no association of pioglitazone and bladder cancer. Colmers et al. [15] in their meta-analysis of RCTs and observational studies stated that, the limited evidence available support the association of bladder cancer and pioglitazone. Zhu et al. [16] in China analyzed only five studies and reported an association of bladder cancer with a cumulative dose of 28gms and 12-24 months duration, the association was stronger with duration >24 months, similar results were obtained by Azoulay et al. [17] in their nested case-control in the United Kingdom, a two years duration association was found by Neumann et al.[18] in a population-based study in France, a more extended period (5years) was reported to be associated with bladder cancer by Mamtani et al. [19] in the US. It is important to note that, the latter study controlled for glycemic control, co-morbidities, and smoking. Hsiao et al. [20] from Taiwan in their nested case-control study identified new cases of bladder cancer and control matched for age and sex and concluded an association on long duration, the study did not assess for confounders including glycemic control. Jin et al. [21] conducted a multi-center study in Korea and found an association of even a small dose (15mg/day for 6 months) is associated with bladder cancer, although the authors controlled for various

confounders including smoking, the fasting plasma sugar they used may not reflect glycemic control over long period and may contribute to the risk of bladder cancer. Similar studies (Song et al, Vallarino et al., Wie et al., Fujimoto et al., Kostapanos et al., Kuo et al., Balaji et al., and Lee et al. [22-30] from Korea, USA, UK, Japan, India, and Taiwan) showed no association between bladder cancer and pioglitazone. A population-based study from Netherlands [31] showed no association of pioglitazone and BC. In contradiction, Turner et al. [32] reviewed five RCTs and 13 observational studies and found an association with bladder cancer among prolonged users of high doses, He et al. [33] concluded similar observation in a meta-analysis of ten studies (one RCT) especially in men. Bosetti et al and Ferwana et al. [34, 35] from Italy and Saudi Arabia in their meta-analyses found an association between bladder cancer and pioglitazone. A recent observational study [36] found no association of pioglitazone and bladder cancer. A more recent multi-population pooled analysis of 4-7.4 years follow-up including 1.01 million [37] showed no cumulative dose effect regarding bladder cancer. Similar results were found by Han et al. [38], Korhonen et al. [39] and Vallabhajosyula et al. [40] in their observational studies. A recent population-based study from UK [41] recruiting a large number of patients and followed for four years reported an association between pioglitazone and bladder cancer, another study [42] from the US observed that the incidence of bladder cancer increased with duration of pioglitazone use in a prevalent cohort, but not an incident cohort, the studies were limited by confounders including glycemic control and smoking. A review conducted in 2017 [43] found an association between bladder cancer and pioglitazone among European males in a dose and duration responsive manner. More recent reviews and meta-analyses showed contradicting results, Yan et al. [44] found an association with bladder cancer, but not in RCTs, while Tang et al. [45] included two RCTs and observational studies and showed the association of pioglitazone with bladder cancer. Furthermore, Tang observed that the association differ by country and funding (if funded by industry or not), Davidson and Pan [46] showed a weak association between bladder cancer and pioglitazone use in 1-2 years duration. A recent study [47] compared pioglitazone users vs. DPP-4 inhibitors (pioglitazone N=38 700), DPP-4s N=82 552, and sulfonylureas N = 126 104) from beneficiary followed for bladder cancer and attenuation after pioglitazone withdrawal and confirmed the association compared to DPP-4 and sulphonylureas and attenuation after the drug withdrawal. The strength of the present review is that

we reviewed all the available literature in the searched databases and detailing the limitations.

The present review limitations were the reviewed articles cannot adjust for several confounders including smoking and diet, and the duration of diabetes mellitus and the degree of glycemic control were not mentioned by the majority of the studies which could affect their results.

Conclusion: The literature reviewed including randomized controlled studies showed contradicting conclusions with some reported an association of pioglitazone use with bladder cancer after a cumulative dose of 28gm, and a duration of 24 months especially among males, while others showed no association. The current study results, the variation of bladder cancer risk by region and ethnicities, and the conflicts of interests raised by some authors call for larger real-world data as RCTs may not be feasible due to ethical consideration.

Implications: Physicians may need to weigh the risks and benefit of pioglitazone use, and limit its use for low-risk patients with the lowest possible dose. Pioglitazone cardio-protective properties should not be ignored especially in patients with stroke.

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Conflicts of interest: None to declare

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